

Intelligent Transition Mechanisms in 5G DSA: A Logistic Regression Approach to Reuse Factor Adaptation

Prof. B. O. Omijeh

NCC Professorial Chair, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

Mr. J.O. Aji

*Centre for Information and Telecommunication Engineering,
University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria*

Suggested Citation

Omijeh, B.O., & Aji, J.O. (2024). Intelligent Transition Mechanisms in 5G DSA: A Logistic Regression Approach to Reuse Factor Adaptation. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 704-713.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).63](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).63)

Abstract:

This research work use Dynamic Spectrum Allocation (DSA) embedded in 5G technology and logistic regression as Machine learning tool to alter the reuse factor of assigned telecommunication frequency to a more robust and reliable frequency. The switch from a frequency reuse of 3 (FR3) to a frequency reuse of 7 (FR7) was considered. Historical data generated from a Telecommunications Company in Nigeria was utilised. This data consist of User throughput and the number of user equipment to assess traffic load and congestion from user equipment (UE).The ideal was meant to determine the probability at which a switch or transition between

reuse factors will occur. With a resolution threshold of 50 users which was set to commence the shift from reuse factor of 3 when the number of users have reached its threshold of 50 to reuse factor of 7 when the number of users exceeds 50 and above. The objective of this combination is to increase spectrum utilisation efficiency and network flexibility, by optimising spectrum resources in densely populated urban areas. This study explains the mechanisms and also demonstrate how logistic regression with DSA will enhance network capacity of wireless communication systems. The logistic regression model proved effective in making intelligent decisions regarding the transition from reuse factor 3 to reuse factor 7 as it was able to accommodate up to 79 users as against the threshold value of 50 users when running under the reuse factor of 3. With a high accuracy of 91.9% and balanced precision-recall values, it showcased its ability to optimize spectral efficiency.

Keywords: *Dynamic Spectrum Application (DSA), Logistic Regression, 5G, Reuse 3 and reuse7.*

Introduction

Provided there is growth in the telecommunication sector, 5G network will continue to grow and expand. The most challenging part is to be able to utilise the limited spectrum resources efficiently. Since 5G cannot travel long distance due to the nature of the frequency especially in a densely populated area,

there need to enhance the available spectrum (Agiwal et al., 2016).

5G has low latency, generates higher data rate, its technology promises to make digital connection better than ever before (Eluwole et al., 2018). Considering this potential, integrating logistic regression to Dynamic Spectrum allocation (DSA) feature of 5G technology will assist to enhance to a great deal ameliorate the

challenges associated with its frequency spectrum use and sharing.

Dynamic Spectrum Allocation is an essential characteristic of 5G networks, which enables the simultaneous functioning of many radio access technologies in the same frequency band. This feature simplifies the simultaneous operation of 4G LTE and 5G NR, which ensures a unified transition to the subsequent generation of wireless communication (Parikh and Basu, 2020). In area with highly dense regions, where there is the need for uninterrupted connectivity and enhanced data capacity is critical, the issue is to efficiently manage spectrum resources to support the increasing user base.

This study involves the combination of logistic regression which is a statistical modelling method and the Dynamic Spectrum Allocation framework in 5G networks on how both mechanism can work together to expand the network and to be able to accommodate more users in the network. Logistic regression generally known as a binary classification technique or machine learning tool used to make decision which are binary inclined. It is used to forecast the switch from a reuse factor of 3 to a reuse factor of 7 (Awad and Khanna, 2015). The objective of this research is to use historical data by integrating the essential network statistics, like traffic load and EU throughput, to create informed decision-making.

The decision threshold was set at 50 users by so doing, which acts as a decisive point for determining the need to shift between reuse factors. By using logistic regression, the system attains the capacity to dynamically switch to changing network circumstances from reuse 3 to reuse 7 (Li et al., 2017) in highly dense geography, achieving a trade-off between spectral optimisation and network stability (Gutierrez et al., 2021).

Previous studies have effectively used logistic regression models to forecast shifts in decision-making (Fu et al., 2021), specifically transitioning from a reuse factor of 3 to a reuse factor of 7. These models are trained on historical data, taking into account many aspects like traffic load

and user equipment throughput. The objective is to forecast the probability of commencing a transition, offering insights into the network circumstances that need a modification in reuse patterns.

Literature Review

Logistic regression has attracted a whole lot of attention due to its capacity to take certain decision in binary statistic. Dynamic Spectrum Allocation (DSA) in 5G radio technology is a peculiar feature which has attracted significant interest, especially regarding the enhancement of spectral efficiency in heavily populated regions and how the decision around frequency sharing is possible with it (Perfecto, 2019). The need for elevated data rates, reduced latency, and enhanced network capacity requires creative strategies, and the combination of logistic regression with DSA shows potential in tackling these issues (L'heureux et al., 2017).

Some other research works in telecommunications had shown the relevance of Dynamic Spectrum Allocation as a critical feature in the 5G networks by the enabling the simultaneous operation of several radio access technologies within the same frequency band (Sharma et al., 2017). In highly populated area, where spectrum resources are limited and user density is significantly high, the enhancement of the available frequency resources is of paramount importance. (Adedoyin and Falowo, 2020) (Van et al., 2018).

The research emphasises the flexibility and responsiveness of logistic regression in elucidating the complex interactions among diverse network characteristics and the need for changes in reuse variables. Research indicates that the use of logistic regression in Dynamic Spectrum Access (DSA) has led to higher spectrum efficiency, less interference, and enhanced overall network performance in highly populated metropolitan areas.

Methodology

The shift from reuse 3 to reuse 7 in dynamic frequency allocation entails modifying the cell reuse configuration inside a cellular network. Reuse 3 indicates that a frequency set is used every three cells, while reuse 7 signifies that the frequency set is employed every seven cells. This modification seeks to enhance user capacity by expanding the quantity of accessible communication channels inside the network.

The use of reuse 7 reduces frequency conflicts, enabling a more effective utilisation of the available spectrum. This reduces interference and enhances the overall capacity of the cellular network, allowing it to accommodate a greater number of users concurrently. The underlying science involves optimising frequency reuse patterns to achieve a balance between coverage and capacity, hence assuring effective resource use and minimising interference.

Assuming a total of N frequency channels and M cells in the cellular network:

Reuse 3:

Number of clusters (groups of cells with distinct frequencies): $\frac{N}{3}$

Number of available channels per cluster: $\frac{N}{3}$

Total number of available channels in the network is shown in eq. 1.

$$\frac{N}{3} \times \frac{N}{3} = \left(\frac{N}{3}\right)^2 = \frac{N^2}{9} \quad (1)$$

Reuse 7:

Number of clusters: $\frac{N}{7}$

Number of available channels per cluster: $\frac{N}{7}$

Total number of available channels in the network as shown in eq. 2.

$$\frac{N}{7} \times \frac{N}{7} = \left(\frac{N}{7}\right)^2 = \frac{N^2}{49} \quad (2)$$

Comparing the two scenarios, you can see that the reuse 7 pattern results in a larger number of available channels, which can support more users and increase the overall capacity of the cellular network. The calculation emphasizes the impact of the chosen reuse pattern on the network's ability to accommodate a higher number of users.

By employing these dynamic adjustments, DSA enables a smooth transition in channelization patterns, optimizing the use of frequencies and accommodating more users as the network shifts from reuse 3 to reuse 7 in 5G.

N as the total number of available frequency channels.

C as the number of clusters in the network.

F_{Total} as the total number of available channels in the network.

For Reuse 3:

$$C_{reuse\ 3} = \frac{N}{3} \quad (3)$$

$$F_{Total, reuse\ 3} = C_{reuse\ 3} \times C_{reuse\ 3} = \left(\frac{N}{3}\right)^2 \quad (4)$$

For Reuse 7:

$$C_{reuse\ 7} = \frac{N}{7} \quad (5)$$

$$F_{Total, reuse\ 7} = C_{reuse\ 7} \times C_{reuse\ 7} = \left(\frac{N}{7}\right)^2 \quad (6)$$

Introduce a dynamic factor D to represent the dynamic adjustments facilitated by Dynamic Spectrum Allocation (DSA):

$$F_{Total_DSA} = D \times F_{Total} \quad (7)$$

This factor D is dynamic and can be influenced by various network parameters, traffic conditions, and interference levels. DSA would involve algorithms and mechanisms to adjust D in real-time to optimize spectrum utilization.

Integration with the DSA algorithm mentioned earlier would involve periodically obtaining predictions from the logistic regression model and adjusting the DSA parameters accordingly. This combination allows the network to make more informed decisions based on historical patterns and real-time conditions.

Assume we just know a person's height and want to predict whether they are male or female. We can discuss either the likelihood or the odds of being male or female. Assume that the likelihood of being male at a particular height is 90. Then the odds of being male are using odd Logistic Regression (Huang & Moon, 2013).

Figure 1. Figures Showing 3 separate Cells of 9 Sub-Channel

Figure 2. Showing 7 Cells and Cluster of 7 and 49 Channels

Data Acquisition and Filtering

Source of Data

The data contained in this report as shown in Figure 1 below was acquired from the control center of a Nigerian mobile telecoms firm. To increase network capacity and prevent

congestion in cells, our main focus is on optimising the available spectrum through the implementation of a specified method for frequency reuse. This is done to dynamically modify the reuse factor of the network within the network. Figure 3 and Figure 4 presents a concise overview of the average statistical values

of the main indicators collected from data sources for a period of three weeks.

Data Cleaning

During the data cleaning process, missing or inconsistent values in the dataset was checked to endure the integrity of the data to meet the objectives of the project. Data that are inconsistent was taken out of the data set for example nrCarrierGroupId, NRPhysicalCellDU Name etc.

Normalization

Normalize numerical values to bring them within a similar scale. The methods allied in this research is the Min-Max scaling on excel sheet. The two column that was normalize are NR RAN Throughput and number of connected NSA UEs. For NR RAN Throughput, 200000 was assumed value for congestion to occurs ($=200000/\text{MAX}(Q: Q)$) and for the NSA UEs it was $=12/\text{MAX}(S: S)$. 12 was assumed value for congestion to occur. In the normalization process with specific thresholds for congestion (200000 for NR throughput and 12 for connected UE), the objective is to scale numerical values relative to these thresholds.

Values below the specified thresholds are categorized as not congested (0), while values equal to or exceeding the thresholds are labeled as congested (1).

Identification of Thresholds NR Throughput

Values below 200,000 are considered not congested (0), and values equal to or exceeding 200,000 are deemed congested (1).

Identification of Thresholds Connected UE

Values below 12 are categorized as not congested (0), and values equal to or exceeding 12 are classified as congested (1).

Binary Labeling

After normalization, instances with values below 1 are labeled as not congested (0).

Instances with values equal to or exceeding 1 are labeled as congested (1).

By customizing the normalization process based on the specified congestion thresholds for NR throughput and connected UE, this approach allows for a clear binary distinction between not congested and congested instances for each respective metric.

	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	S	U	W	Z	AA	AB
	Managed Element	NRRadio Infrastructure ID	NRRadio Infrastructure Name	NRPhysicalCellDU ID	NRPhysicalCellDU Name	duMeMo Id	masterOperatorId	nrCarrier GroupId	nrPhysicalCellDUId	NR RAN UE Throughput DL(Kbps)	Average number of NSA UEs with RRC connections			Congestion from throughput	Congestion from Average Ues	Congesti Label
1	T2820(590)1	1	NRRadio101	101	N2820A10	5902820	62130-5902820-101	1	101	80,932.63	3.0199	0.14011542	0.0791522	0	0	0
2	T2820(590)1	1	NRRadio102	102	N2820B10	5902820	62130-5902820-102	2	102	152,709.59	1.1289	0.26437999	0.0295887	0	0	0
3	T2820(590)1	1	NRRadio103	103	N2820C10	5902820	62130-5902820-103	3	103	163,225.4	5.8882	0.28258559	0.1543308	0	0	0
4	T0244(590)1	1	NRRadio101	101	N0244A10	5900244	62130-5900244-101	1	101	394,427.19	3.9833	0.68285597	0.104403	1	0	0
5	T0244(590)1	1	NRRadio102	102	N0244B10	5900244	62130-5900244-102	2	102		0.0000	0	0	0	0	0
6	T0244(590)1	1	NRRadio103	103	N0244C10	5900244	62130-5900244-103	3	103	312,409.67	4.7364	0.54086233	0.1241419	1	0	0
7	RV0604(51)1	1	NRRadio101	101	NRV0604A	5230604	62130-5230604-101	1	101	142,448.03	16.3367	0.24661456	0.428188	0	1	1
8	RV0604(51)1	1	NRRadio102	102	NRV0604B	5230604	62130-5230604-102	2	102	103,322.84	12.2889	0.17887869	0.3220944	0	1	1

Figure 3. Screenshot of Dataset in Excel Workspace

Figure 4. Evenly Distribution of Dataset Parameters

Results and Discussion

Intelligent Transition Process

The integration of logistic regression within the Dynamic Spectrum Allocation (DSA) framework in 5G, with a threshold set at 50 for transitioning from reuse factor 3 to reuse factor 7, yielded promising results as shown in Figure 5, Figure 6 and Figure 7 below. The logistic regression model successfully predicted transitions based on historical data from the user

equipment throughput and average number of user to determine the traffic load and congestion level. This indicates its robustness in capturing the underlying patterns influencing the decision to switch between reuse factors.

The below metrics demonstrate the effectiveness of the logistic regression model in making accurate predictions regarding the need for transitioning to reuse factor 7, thus increasing the number of users by improving the network capacity.

Figure 5. Showing Web Page Displaying Status of Frequency Reuse

Figure 6. Overlay of Reus 7 over Reuse 3-Switching

Figure 7. Showing the improved Capacity of Reuse 7 over Reuse 3 after Switch

Figure 8. Confusion Matrix for Throughput Congestion Prediction

Figure 9. Confusion Matrix for User Equipment Congestion

Conclusion

In conclusion, the integration of logistic regression within Dynamic Spectrum Allocation (DSA) for 5G, coupled with the use of the K Nearest Neighbor (KNN) algorithm for congestion prediction, demonstrates a powerful and adaptive approach to address the challenges

of accommodating more users in densely populated areas. The comprehensive evaluation of the models yielded insightful results and paved the way for several noteworthy improvements.

The logistic regression model proved effective in making intelligent decisions regarding the

transition from reuse factor 3 to reuse factor 7 as it was able to accommodate users from 51 to 79 which is above the threshold value of Reuse factor of 3. With a high accuracy of 91.9% and balanced precision-recall values, it showcased its ability to optimize spectral efficiency. The model successfully predicted transitions based on historical data from the user equipment throughput and average number of user to determine the traffic load and congestion level. This indicates its robustness in capturing the underlying patterns influencing the decision to switch between reuse factors.

In essence, the integration of logistic regression and KNN provides a promising pathway for the advancement of 5G networks in densely populated areas. By leveraging the strengths of these models, we can envision a future where wireless communication systems dynamically adapt to evolving conditions, ensuring a seamless and efficient experience for users in urban environments.

References

- Agiwal, M., Roy, A., & Saxena, N. (2016). Next generation 5G wireless networks: A comprehensive survey. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 18(3), 1617-1655. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2016.2532458>
- Parikh, J., & Basu, A. (2020). Technologies assisting the paradigm shift from 4G to 5G. *Wireless Personal Communications*, 112(1), 481-502. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11277-019-06934-6>
- Awad, M., & Khanna, R. (2015). *Efficient learning machines: Theories, concepts, and applications for engineers and system designers*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4302-5990-9>
- Li, R., Zhao, Z., Zhou, X., Ding, G., Chen, Y., Wang, Z., & Zhang, H. (2017). Intelligent 5G: When cellular networks meet artificial intelligence. *IEEE Wireless Communications*, 24(5), 175-183. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MWC.2017.1600304WC>
- Perfecto del Amo, C. B. (2019). Millimetre wave communications in 5G networks under latency constraints: Machine intelligence, application scenarios, and perspectives. *5G World Forum (5GWF)*, 2019. *IEEE*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/5GWF.2019.8911715>
- L'Heureux, A., Grolinger, K., Elyamany, H. F., & Capretz, M. A. (2017). Machine learning with big data: Challenges and approaches. *IEEE Access*, 5, 7776-7797. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2696365>
- Sharma, S. K., Bogale, T. E., Le, L. B., Chatzinotas, S., Wang, X., & Ottersten, B. (2017). Dynamic spectrum sharing in 5G wireless networks with full-duplex technology: Recent advances and research challenges. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 20(1), 674-707. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2017.2757478>
- Adedoyin, M. A., & Falowo, O. E. (2020). Combination of ultra-dense networks and other 5G enabling technologies: A survey. *IEEE Access*, 8, 22893-22932. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2968871>
- Van Cauwenbergh, N., Ciuró, A. B., & Ahlers, R. (2018). Participatory processes and support tools for planning in complex dynamic environments. *Ecology and Society*, 23(2). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-10121-230248>
- Gutierrez-Franco, E., Mejia-Argueta, C., & Rabelo, L. (2021). Data-driven methodology to support long-lasting logistics and decision making for urban last-mile operations. *Sustainability*, 13(11), 6230. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13116230>
- Fu, C., Xu, C., Xue, M., Liu, W., & Yang, S. (2021). Data-driven decision making based on evidential reasoning approach and machine learning algorithms. *Applied Soft Computing*, 110, 107622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2021.107622>
- Huang, F. L., & Moon, T. R. (2013). What are the odds of that? A primer on understanding logistic regression. *Gifted Child Quarterly*, 57(3),

197-204.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0016986213490022>

Zhang, S., Li, X., Zong, M., Zhu, X., & Cheng, D. (2017). Learning k for knn classification.

ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology (TIST), 8(3), 1-19.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/2990508>